

Governmental measures regarding COVID-19: Are Germany's right-wing populists losing out while the government gains support?

Author: Melanie Weissenberg, ERC PRIME Youth Project Researcher, European Institute, Istanbul Bilgi University; and PhD Candidate in Political Science, Istanbul Bilgi University

If general elections would take place next Sunday, Germany's right-wing populist party AfD (Alternative for Germany) would be backed by ten percent or less losing between one to two percent of its voters. Meanwhile, the coalition government is more popular than ever: Merkel's conservative CDU (Christian-Democratic Union) would get 37 percent of the votes and thus gain between seven and eleven percent. The SPD (Social Democrats) would gain between one and three percent with a total share of 17 percent.[i] The latest opinion polls by *infratest dimap* show a new political trend in Germany: A vast majority of Germany's citizens is satisfied or very satisfied (72 %) with the government's work to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic. In comparison, poll numbers of the first March week show almost the opposite: only 35 percent were satisfied with the federal government's policies, while 65 percent were dissatisfied.[ii]

It is not that astonishing that the AfD's popularity decreases while there is a general satisfaction in the population concerning the government's policies of handling COVID-19. The right-wing populists' response to COVID-19 and internal quarrels, however, may also have contributed to its decreasing popularity.

Despite the global pandemic crisis, pertinent warnings and contact restrictions, the AfD has repeatedly called for gatherings and ignored recommendations of keeping social distance. In the light of sinking poll numbers, party representatives called for an extraordinary meeting during the Easter break last week to discuss 'further actions in the Corona crisis' and to create a 'link to the key issues of the AfD'. 70 of the 89 AfD representatives gathered in the parliament against the will of the chairpersons Alice Weidel and Alexander Gauland.[iii] A couple of weeks earlier, the party forced the whole parliament of Saxony to gather, despite suggestions by members of the other parties to decrease the number of representatives in the parliament.[iv]

As the corona crisis is the main political issue at the moment, the topics the party feeds from – the fight against refugees, Islam and the European Union – become irrelevant. In addition, the party struggles with finding a united

Published: April 17, 2020, 11:09 a.m.

Edited: April 17, 2020, 11:12 a.m.

[See all BLOG](#)

Share

stance concerning political measures in response to COVID-19 and its propositions are late or vague: While some of the AfD's representatives agreed with the government's measures in managing COVID-19, others criticized the government and demanded state subsidies for the national economy. AfD Party leader Chrupalla presented a Germany-pact for economic aid while the German parliament was gathering and already passing a respective law.[v]

Meanwhile, the AfD also had internal quarrels concerning its leadership and directions. In the beginning of March, the Federal Intelligence Agency decided to observe the party's ethnic (*völkisch*[vi])-national "wing" under the leadership of Björn Höcke due to its ultra-right-wing extremist tendencies. [vii] After the party's federal executive committee demanded the dissolution of the "wing" by the end of April, party leader Meuthen proposed the party to split into a "social-patriotic" and a "liberal-conservative" wing, a split that would also have meant an east-west division.[viii] After strong criticism, Meuthen was forced to withdraw his idea.[ix]

Additionally, the party's strategy of representing independent media as delivering false information while social media are represented as an alternative mass medium containing factual information is no longer working. Alternative facts are less popular at the moment, as many increasingly use established media, research institutes and public health authorities to inform themselves about COVID-19. Now more people than ever seem to be interested in assessments by virologists and other researchers. An analysis shows that COVID-19 related topics of the AfD are not popular among party supporters. The AfD's weakest Facebook posts of the last weeks were mostly about Corona. Weakened algorithms decrease the party's visibility and range in social media.[x] Against this backdrop glitches as the following do not help: At the end of March, the party announced a donation of masks from members of the state parliament to the Dresden University Hospital without revealing the donator. After party representatives turned the act of handing over the masks into a PR campaign for their supporters the hospital donated the masks to Dresden's ambulance for refugees, stating that it felt "politically instrumentalized".[xi]

Despite these possible causes for the AfD's decreased popularity, there is no reason to be optimistic. The drop in the AfD's poll ratings should be situated in a broader decrease in support for the opposition parties. According to the opinion polls, the Green Party, the Left Party and the Free Democratic Party (FDP) would also lose a significant share of voters.[xii] Moreover, these tendencies may not last. With the long duration of the emergency, and an upcoming recession, things may change again. After all, the rhetoric of the AfD is based on fear, discontent and frustration, all feelings that may be triggered in times of economic hardship. The AfD's electoral base is comprised of people at economic risk who are likely to experience these feelings: workers, employees, middle-classes and self-employed people.[xiii]

[i] Forsa (2020) Wenn am nächsten Sonntag Bundestagswahl wäre ..., Umfragen. Available at: <https://www.wahlrecht.de/umfragen/forsa.htm> (Accessed: 16 April 2020); infratest dimap (2020) Sonntagsfrage (bundesweit) vom 02.04.2020, infratest dimap. Available at: <https://www.infratest-dimap.de/umfragen-analysen/bundesweit/sonntagsfrage/> (Accessed: 16 April 2020).

[ii] Ehni, E. (2020) Deutschland Trend: Großes Vertrauen in Merkel und Co., Tagesschau.de

[iii] Bauer, K. (2020) 'Corona und die AfD: In der Pandemie verliert die AfD an Anziehungskraft', Stuttgarter Zeitung, 9 April. Available at: <https://www.stuttgarter-zeitung.de/inhalt.corona-und-die-afd-in-der-pandemie-verliert-die-afd-an-anziehungskraft.8e145756-8326-42e4-a20f-3a2e156bf994.html>; Steffen, T. (2020) 'AfD und Corona: Das Ende der alten

Sicherheiten', Zeit Online, 9 April. Available at: <https://www.zeit.de/politik/deutschland/2020-04/afd-coronavirus-strategie-krise-migranten-covid-19/komplettansicht>.

[iv] Bartsch, M. (2020) 'Extreme Rechte in Zeiten des Coronavirus: Die AfD blamiert sich in der Krise', taz, 18 March. Available at: <https://taz.de/Extreme-Rechte-in-Zeiten-des-Coronavirus/!5672341/>.

[v] Steffen, T. (2020) (see above) [vi] 'völkisch' is an adjective for the people as an ethnic group (*Volk*). The term was in frequent use by the National Socialists and revived by the AfD.

[vii] Tagesschau.de (2020) Verfassungsschutz zu AfD-"Flügel": Erwiesen rechtsextrem, Tagesschau.de. Available at: <https://www.tagesschau.de/inland/afd-fluegel-verfassungsschutz-101.html> (Accessed: 16 April 2020). [viii] Tagesschau (2020) Streit um AfD-Spaltung Parteichef Meuthen räumt Fehler ein, MDR Aktell.

[ix] Ibid [x] Fiedler, M. (2020) '„Die Wutmaschine funktioniert nicht mehr“ Warum die AfD in der Corona-Krise an Reichweite verliert', Der Tagesspiegel, 7 April. Available at: <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/themen/agenda/die-wutmaschine-funktioniert-nicht-mehr-warum-die-afd-in-der-corona-krise-an-reichweite-verliert/25720228.html>.

[xi] Laschyk, T. (2020) AfD PR-Aktion wird Eigentor, Volksverpetzer. Available at: <https://www.volksverpetzer.de/bericht/afd-klink-masken/> (Accessed: 16 April 2020); Redaktionsnetzwerk Deutschland (2020) AfD lässt Masken für Klinik nähern – die fühlt sich ausgenutzt, Redaktionsnetzwerk Deutschland.

[xii] Ibid.

[xiii] Niedermayer, O. and Hofrichter, J. (2016) 'Die Wählerschaft der AfD: Wer ist sie, woher kommt sie und wie weit rechts steht sie?', Zeitschrift für Parlamentsfragen, 42(2), pp. 267–284. doi: 10.5771/0340-1758-2016-2-267.

Authors:

Melanie Weissenberg

bilgierc@bilgi.edu.tr

Phone: 0212 311 5363

